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Reconciling the Just and Sustainable City in the Era of Just Transition: A Review of Urban Visions

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Abstract

Just transition occupies an increasingly important place in political agendas from global to local levels. In recent years, this concept has evolved from a reactive *social* project aimed at protecting industrial workers affected by environmental regulations to a proactive *social-ecological* project aimed at simultaneously reducing social inequalities and environmental degradation. This ambition of bridging social justice and sustainability objectives is particularly relevant for the urban context, where social and environmental issues tend to concentrate and intertwine. However, questions of what a just *and* sustainable city could and should look like remain largely unexplored. While there exist several urban visions that centre social justice (most notably Susan Fainstein's "Just City"), sustainability issues are not central to these visions. At the same time, it remains unclear whether and how urban visions that do focus on sustainability (e.g., sustainable cities, eco-cities, green cities, low-carbon cities...) consider social justice concerns. This research has two main goals: first, to identify and analyse the role of sustainability in the prominent just city visions and, second, to examine visions of sustainable cities and their conceptualization of justice. The research is based on an analysis of several seminal texts on just cities and sustainable city visions. The visions are analysed through a framework that highlights considerations of distributional, procedural and recognition-based justice. By analysing the place of sustainability within just city visions and the place of social justice in sustainable city visions, we give direction to and open discussion about the contours of possible just *and* sustainable urban futures.

1. Introduction

Since its emergence in the 1990s in the American trade union world (Jones, 2022 ; Ciptet, 2022 ; Stevis and Felli, 2020), the concept of just transition has occupied an increasingly important place in political agendas, as evidenced by its integration as a guiding principle in the Paris Agreement in 2015 and the adoption by the United Kingdom, the European Union, Canada, New Zealand, Norway and the United States of the COP 26 Just Transition Declaration in 2021 (Jones, 2022 ; Ciptet, 2022 ; Galgóczi 2022; Abram et al., 2022 ; Stevis and Felli, 2020). The internationalisation of this concept and its rise in popularity among a large number of actors, including trade unions, environmental (justice) movements, governments and companies (Wilgosh et al, 2022 ; Galgóczi 2022 ; Stevis and Felli, 2020 ; Córdova et al., 2022), have contributed to the emergence of a plurality of conceptions of just transition (La Gioia et al., 2023 ; Cha and Pastor, 2022 ; Krause et al., 2022 ; Burke 2022 ; Galgóczi 2022 ; Wang and Lo, 2021 ; Jones, 2022 ; Stevis and Felli, 2020), but also to a broadening of its meaning (Luke, 2023 ; Burke 2022 ; Abram et al., 2022 ; Bauler et al., 2021). Just transition has evolved from a narrow *social* project aimed at protecting workers in polluting industries affected by environmental regulations (Wilgosh et al, 2022 ; Abram et al., 2022) to a comprehensive *eco-social* project aimed at jointly pursuing environmental *and* social justice objectives (Krause et al., 2022 ; Ciptet, 2022 ; Cha and Pastor, 2022 ; Burke 2022 ; Bauler et al., 2021 ; Clarke and Lipsig-Mummé, 2020).

The rationale underlying the comprehensive approach to just transition - the one on which this paper is founded¹ - is that sustainability and justice objectives are highly interconnected. On the one hand, environmental imperatives represent an opportunity to reduce existing inequalities and to transition towards a more just society (Krause et al., 2022 ; Cha and Pastor, 2022 ; Abram et al., 2022 ; Galgóczi 2022), and, on the other hand, less inequalities can facilitate and accelerate the transition to a sustainable society notably by improving the social acceptability of environmental policies (Laurent, 2023 ; Krause et al., 2022 ; Stevis and Felli, 2020). This comprehensive approach to just transition is found, among others, in the *Build Back Better* framework adopted in the UK and US, whose objective is to address the socio-economic impacts of the COVID-19 crisis by simultaneously reducing environmental degradation and long-standing inequalities (Lacey-Barnacle et al., 2023), but also in the US Green New Deal, which aims to decarbonize the economy while improving justice by promoting, inter alia, adequate housing, quality food and health care for all (Cha and Pastor, 2022).

The increasing political interest in just transition goes hand in hand with the development of a growing body of research on the issue (Abram et al., 2022). This research stream includes historical studies on the emergence and evolutions of the concept of just transition (Córdova et al., 2022 ; Henry et al., 2020 ; Felli and Stevis, 2014), work aimed at developing conceptual and analytical frameworks for the just transition (Heffron and McCauley, 2018 ; McCauley and Heffron, 2018), analysis of the discourses and visions of the just transition (La Gioia et al., 2023 ; Wilgosh et al., 2022 ; Barnes et al., 2022 ; Cahill and Allen, 2020 ; Didier, 2020 ; Morena et al., 2018), research sketching avenues for governing just transition (Tschersich and Kok, 2022 ; Bauler et al., 2021 ; Schwanen, 2021 ; Laurent, 2021 ; Routledge, 2018), and empirical studies exploring how just transition imperatives are translated into practice in specific strategies, like the EU Green Deal (Filipovic et al., 2022), places (Santos Ayllón and Jenkins, 2023 ; McCauley et al., 2023 ; Berglund et al., 2023) or sectors, and more particularly in emitting industries targeted by the decarbonisation of the economy like coal or automobile (Luke, 2023 ; Banerjee and Schuitema, 2022 ; Galgóczi, 2022 ; Bainton et al., 2021). While the body of literature on just transition is growing, some issues remain underexplored (Abram et al., 2022). This is particularly the case for just transitions at the urban scale or “Just urban transitions”. While there is an established

¹ In the field of sustainability transitions studies, transitions refer to “long-term, multi-dimensional, and fundamental transformation processes through which established socio-technical systems shift to more sustainable modes of production and consumption” (Markard et al. 2012, p. 956). In this paper, we focus on a specific aspect of transitions, namely their normative orientations (see Köhler et al., 2019). We explore the just and sustainable futures that transitions seek to achieve, and not the process of transformation allowing us to reach such futures.

body of literature on urban justice (see for e.g.: Fainstein, 2014 ; Fincher and Iveson, 2012 ; Steil and Connolly, 2009) and on urban sustainability transitions (see for e.g.: Frantzeskaki et al., 2017 ; Loorbach et al., 2016 ; Bulkeley and Betsill, 2006), research exploring the intersections between justice and sustainability transitions concerns at the city level remains relatively rare (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019).

Yet, the city is a particularly relevant level of analysis when considering just transitions. With the expected continuation of urbanisation that began during the Industrial Revolution, the share of the European populations living in urban areas is expected to increase from 75% to 84% between now and 2050 (European Commission, 2020a; European Commission, 2020b). As a result, “the future of the most of humanity now lies, for the first time in history, fundamentally in urbanising areas. The qualities of urban living in the 21st century will define the qualities of civilisation itself” (Harvey, 1996, p. 403). Considering just transitions at the urban scale is even more relevant since cities are responsible for the vast majority of contemporary environmental problems, including climate change, air and water pollution, biodiversity loss, resource depletion and waste production (Steele and Dodson, 2022 ; Jänicke, 2015). Cities are notably responsible for more than 70% of global CO₂ emissions, a large part of which are associated with their fossil fuel-intensive industrial and transportation systems (Dasgupta et al., 2022). In turn, environmental problems disproportionately affect vulnerable urban residents (De Muynck and Ragot, 2022 ; Shen et al., 2020), thus contributing to widening existing inequalities in cities (Steele and Dodson, 2022 ; Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019 ; Béné et al., 2017). In fact, cities have historically concentrated many forms of injustices and inequalities (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019). It is also at this scale that “questions of justice are felt concretely as part of everyday life” (Connolly and Steil 2009, p. 6). Inequalities in cities have grown from the 1970s following the advent of the “Neoliberal City” (Dlabac et al. 2022 ; Granberg and Glover, 2021; Connolly and Steil 2009 ; Novy and Mayer 2009), and even more in recent years due to the increasingly perceptible impacts of climate change, but also as a result of the socio-economic consequences of the COVID-19 crisis (Steele and Dodson, 2022) and the explosion in energy prices associated with the war in Ukraine (Galgóczi, 2022). In this context, more and more cities are committed to ensuring a just transition (Steele and Dodson, 2022 ; Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019). Owing to the above-mentioned research gap on just urban transitions (aiming to bridge environmental and social justice objectives), there is, however, “a lack of frameworks and tools to support city actors to understand and implement just transitions, partly resulting in high level commitments to climate justice but limited operationalisation or detailed analysis” (Berglund et al. 2023, p.12).

Amidst a relative scarcity of research on just urban transitions a compelling contribution is the *Research Agenda for Just Urban Transitions* elaborated by Hughes and Hoffmann (2019). The authors consider that four strains of justice scholarship are necessary to inform research on just urban transitions, namely urban, environmental, climate and energy justice. In fact, each of these scholarships focuses on specific aspects of just urban transitions, and their articulation intends to provide a comprehensive conceptual framework for just urban transitions. Urban justice emerged in the early 1970s, notably under the impetus of the critical political economy analyses *Social Justice and the City* from David Harvey’s (1973) and *The Urban Question* from Manuel Castells (1972), “as an attempt to rethink the links between space, development, power, and planning” (Yiftachel et al. 2009, p. 122). As will be explained in more depth in the next section (see Section 3), urban justice literature has since expanded to cover issues such as the recognition of differences, diversity and multiculturalism in urban planning processes (Fainstein, 2014 ; Fincher and Iveson, 2012 ; Connolly and Steil, 2009 ; Yiftachel et al. 2009). Another prominent branch of scholarship informing the just urban transition is that of environmental justice. Initially developed in the late 1970s for denouncing the unequal distribution of environmental impacts and risks (Jenkins, 2018; Evans and Phelan, 2016; Ballet et al., 2015; McCauley et al., 2013; Schlosberg, 2007), the environmental justice scholarship has since evolved to cover a broader spectrum of issues, including inequalities of access to green spaces, living environment, mobility, health and food, as well as inequalities of public participation and interpellation on the experienced inequalities (Laigle, 2018; Jenkins, 2018; Schlosberg, 2007). The climate justice

literature, which emerged in the 1990s alongside environmental justice scholarship (Williams and Doyon, 2019; Jenkins, 2018; Heffron and McCauley, 2017), addressed the “triple inequity” of mitigation, responsibility, and vulnerability associated with the climate problem (Jenkins 2018, p. 118), emphasising justice for people in developing countries and for future generations (McCauley et al. 2013). Until now, climate justice debates have largely occurred at the international scale, yet there is a need to bring these debates to the urban scale to understand how climate change could exacerbate or mitigate structural urban inequalities (Bulkeley et al., 2014). Finally, the most recent of these four scholarships, energy justice, which emerged around early 2013 (Heffron and McCauley, 2017), focuses on justice issues across the energy life cycle, both from a production- and consumption-based perspective (Heffron and McCauley, 2018; McCauley and Heffron, 2018). It thus deals with issues such as the disparities in access to energy services and energy efficiency technologies, the unequal distribution of burdens of the energy system as well as the distributive and procedural injustices in renewable energy planning (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019; McCauley et al., 2019; Sovacool et al., 2017; Sovacool and Dworkin, 2015). While urban, environmental, climate and energy justice focus on different (but interrelated) justice issues, they tend to be built on the same justice dimensions, namely distributive justice, procedural justice and justice as recognition (Wang and Lo, 2021 ; Williams and Doyon, 2019; Heffron and McCauley, 2017; Bouzarovski and Simcock, 2017; Jenkins et al. 2016; Ballet et al., 2015; McCauley et al. 2013; Schlosberg, 2007).

Based on a review of these four strains of justice scholarship and of the literature on just transition in general, Hughes and Hoffmann (2019) show that the consideration of environmental issues in the literature on urban justice and that of justice issues in the literature on urban sustainability transitions are only at their infancy, but also that most research on just urban transitions is retrospective and evaluative; analyses on the topic are mainly aimed at denouncing injustices and gaps in current policies so that these can be addressed (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019). In that vein, we find, for instance, a study on the existing inequalities in exposure and vulnerability to climate risks in Brussels conducted by De Muynck and Ragot (2022), as well as a critical analysis of the development and implementation of just transition strategies in three cities in the South West of England carried out by Berglund et al. (2023). Hughes and Hoffmann (2019) show, however, that future-oriented analyses on just urban transitions are lacking. Yet, to support cities in the elaboration and implementation of just transition, it is essential to move “beyond diagnosing injustices and building a positive case for, and pathways to, just and equitable low carbon cities” (Hughes and Hoffmann 2019, p.2). This involves notably the following questions: What could a just *and* sustainable city look like? What policies could be developed and implemented to ensure just urban transitions? By which actors? How can we monitor and evaluate these transition processes?

The main objective of this paper is to contribute to this reflection by exploring what a just *and* sustainable city might look like based on a review of urban visions. An urban vision is here understood as an image of a desirable future of the city that can help to critique the present situation and to create an alternative future. It can be associated with utopian urbanism which involves the “expression of desire for a better way of being and living through the imagining of a different city and a different urban life” (Pinder 2002, p.230). Urban visions, which played a fundamental role in the fabric of the modernist city in the twentieth century (Pinder, 2005), can today contribute to just urban transitions. Due to their potentially disruptive attributes, urban visions can indeed promote transformations by inspiring critical thinking and political action as explained by David Pinder: “The break with the here and now that such utopianism enacts can create space for challenging what is, for disrupting dominant assumptions about social and spatial organisation, and for imagining other possibilities and desires. It can thus be subversive, stimulating demands for action and political practice, exploring how things might be different” (Pinder 2002, p. 239). Such urban visions can be put into dialogue, challenged and modified (Pinder, 2002). In this sense, we consider them more as a dynamic and open process than as a static destination (Tuiskunen et al., 2015).

In this review of urban visions, we focus more specifically on “just city” and “sustainable city” visions. Here we consider a “sustainable city” vision as a vision that prioritises explicitly one or several environmental objectives. Such a vision can also pursue social and economic objectives, with different degrees of emphasis. In that case, “sustainable city” visions can overlap with “just city” visions. While there exist several seminal just urban visions, most notably Susan Fainstein’s “Just City”, environmental objectives tend not to be central to these visions. On the other hand, the justice imperatives in different sustainable urban visions (e.g., sustainable cities, eco-cities, green cities, low-carbon cities...) are less clear. This research thus aims to analyse how environmental concerns are taken into account in the most influential “just city” visions, and, conversely, how the social justice issues are considered in the main visions of the “sustainable city”. Based on this analysis, we aim to explore how ambitions of these visions may come together to inform the development of “Just Urban Transition” visions, or urban visions that centre both justice *and* sustainability objectives.

The following section introduces the methodology adopted for identifying and analysing “Just City” and “Sustainable City” visions. Sections 3 and 4 present respectively the review of “Just City” and “Sustainable City” visions. Section 5 analyses whether and how the reviewed visions consider sustainability and justice objectives. Section 6 corresponds to the discussion and conclusion. It outlines elements of reflection for the development of “Just Urban Transition” visions reconciling justice and sustainability objectives and identifies avenues for future research.

2. Methodology

As previously mentioned, this research is based on a review of “just city” and “sustainable city” visions. The review considers visions elaborated for developed and formally democratic countries of the Western World, mainly from the beginning of 1990’s, which corresponds to the time when urban scholars began to carry out explicitly normative work on justice in the city (Fainstein, 2014). This review focuses more specifically on the visions of “just city” and “sustainable city” conceptualised in the academic field. It therefore does not consider the implementation of the reviewed visions in real-world examples, though there are several cases of cities that have developed and adopted some of them (e.g., eco-cities or circular cities). Yet, significant disparities exist between the conceptualization of these visions and their empirical manifestations. *In fine*, the visions considered in this review are in no way exhaustive, but rather aim to present a range of (often-cited) “just city” and “sustainable city” visions, at different moments in time.

We have identified the visions of “just city” to be analysed starting from the seminal text *The Just City* published in 2010 by Susan Fainstein. We looked for influential visions of “just city” that inspired and have been inspired by Fainstein’s contribution. We consider as influential visions those that are usually mentioned in the analyses tracing the evolution of the academic debate around the “just city”, like Marcuse (2009), Fainstein (2014) and several literature reviews presented in recent academic papers on the issue (e.g.: Granberg and Glover, 2021 ; Perry and Atherton, 2017). In doing so, we have identified the following texts: *Social Justice and the City* (Harvey, 1973), *Justice and the Politics of Difference* (Young, 1990), *Towards Cosmopolis: Planning for Multicultural Cities* (Sandercock, 1997), *Planning in the Face of Power* (Forester, 1988), *Seeking Spatial Justice* (Soja, 2010), and *The Good City: In Defense of Utopian Thinking* (Friedmann, 2000).

The visions of “sustainable city” to be analysed were identified based on the bibliometric analyses of concepts promoting urban sustainable transitions carried out by de Jong et al. (2015) and Fu and Zhang (2017). Among the visions identified in these analyses, we selected the five that Fu and Zhang (2017) considered to be the most important according to their occurrence in scientific databases, namely “Sustainable city”, “Smart city”, “Eco-city”, “Low-carbon city” and “Green city”. This list has been completed with two additional visions: the “Resilient city” and the “Circular city”. The aforementioned bibliometric analyses reveal that the resilient city is hardly deliberated in the literature, but it has been included in this review because the transition towards a resilient city is a crucial question in the context

of just urban transitions and in the context of climate change. The “Circular city” was not identified at all in the two bibliometric analyses. This can be explained by the fact that these analyses were published in 2015 and 2017, when the “Circular city” vision was not as popular as it is today. A recent bibliometric analysis on circular economy research shows, in fact, that 90% of the articles on the topic have been published between 2015 and 2019, thus highlighting recent academic interest in this concept (Goyal et al., 2021). Finally, note that many hybrid forms of these “Sustainable city” visions exist (e.g., “Smart sustainable city”), but we have decided to limit the analysis to singular visions.

For each “just city” and “sustainable city” vision selected, we have summarised their main characteristics, before analysing if and how they integrate the different just transition objectives, or, to put it differently, if and how they integrate sustainability *and* justice objectives. We focused more specifically on the consideration of sustainability objectives in the visions of the “just city”, and, on the contrary, on the consideration of justice objectives in the visions of the “sustainable city”. With that aim in mind, we used an analytical framework grasping the main distributive, procedural and recognitional justice dimensions considered in urban, environmental, climate and energy justice scholarships. As explained in Section 1, the combination of these four scholarships provides a comprehensive conceptual framework for just urban transitions (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019).

3. Review of the “Just City” Visions

Social equity entered the political agenda of cities in the Western world around the middle of the 19th century (Dlabac et al., 2022 ; Reece, 2018) in the context of urbanisation associated with the industrial revolution (Granberg and Glover, 2021). Since then, equity planning practices and theories have developed and co-evolved in response to various social and economic factors, such as the sanitary and safety problems of crowded urban tenements, the socio-economic impacts of the Great Depression, the racial discrimination associated with waves of immigration, or the disproportionate displacement of marginalised groups as part of urban renewal. Those factors and their influence on equity planning practices and theories have been traced in detail notably by Reece (2018) who distinguishes four eras of equity planning practices and theories: the “Progressive Era” between the late 19th and early 20th Century, the “New Deal Era” in the 1930s, the “Advocacy Planning Era” in the 1960s and 1970s, and the “Just City Era” from 2000.

Despite the growing political attention on urban social injustice, it is only in the 1990s that theoretical works aimed at sketching visions of the “Just city” started to emerge (Fainstein, 2014). Indeed, while works in political philosophy like those of John Rawls, Amartya Sen or Martha Nussbaum did not specify neither how the proposed principles of justice could be concretely operationalized (Connolly and Steil, 2009), nor how they could address urban and spatial issues (Dlabac et al., 2022), research carried out in the behavioural social sciences has rested for many years on a positivist paradigm, staying away from normative statements (Fainstein, 2014).

In this section, we review seminal visions of “just city” developed since the 1990s by distinguishing three main currents of thought: the cultural turn, the communicative turn and the “Just City” Era. One of the major distinctions between these three currents concerns the emphasis they place on distributive justice, procedural justice, and justice as recognition. While the cultural and communicative theorists prioritise, respectively, justice as recognition and procedural justice, many visions developed in the “Just city” Era, starting from Fainstein’s vision, tend to give priority to distributive justice. As will be illustrated later, tensions between these three governing principles exist, which leads several authors to establish priorities (Fainstein, 2010).

To these three currents, we have added the radical political economy critique. It seemed relevant to consider this current even if it adopts a normative posture only in an implicit way and does therefore not propose visions of “just city” *per se*, because its seminal texts and their authors played an important role in the academic debates on the “just city”. The more prominent contributions of the

radical political economy critique have often constituted a starting point for the elaboration of visions of the “just city”. In turn, the authors of these contributions have discussed the visions of the “just city” and the critiques of their work on which they are based.

3.1. The Radical Political Economy Critique

In the 1960s and 1970, in a context marked by revolts notably against urban renewal projects, the lack of public service and police violence, leftist researchers started to denounce and tackle injustices in the cities, and to integrate in this way a moral dimension in their work. These researchers, however, did not explicitly define normative “Just City” criteria (Fainstein, 2014). An influential contribution from this time is that of Henry Lefebvre (1967) who, through the concept of “Right to the city”, advocates a right to participate in the construction of the city.

In the 1970s, in the continuation of Henry Lefebvre's work, an interdisciplinary community of researchers, including notably the neo-Marxists David Harvey (1973) and Manuel Castells (1972), has developed a tradition of urban studies research based on political economic epistemology (Fainstein, 2014 ; Yiftachel et al. 2009). These scholars explore “how power relations (as determined by the interaction between state authority, economic ownership, and urban residents) affect urban outcomes and, in particular, how spatial relations reinforce injustice” (Fainstein 2014, p. 2). They attack the economic and political power imbalances inherent in capitalist systems that they consider as a root cause of urban injustice (Fainstein, 2014 ; Connolly and Steil, 2009). While Castells limits himself to the analysis of injustices, David Harvey advocates for “alternative modes of production, consumption, and distribution that would reorganize the class structure of society” (Connolly and Steil 2009, p. 4) with a view to building a more just city. He, however, does not conceptualise criteria of justice (Fainstein, 2014).

3.2. The Cultural Turn

The emphasis of Marxist theory on classes has been criticised in the context of the “cultural turn” that took place in the 1990s in the field of urban political economy. The empirical works, like those of the philosophers Iris Marion Young (1990) and Nancy Fraser (1999), have demonstrated the need to consider other dimensions like race, ethnicity, gender or sexuality as key factors in unequal distribution of resources and power in the cities (Connolly and Steil, 2009). These calls for justice as recognition of difference have been accompanied by efforts for defining urban justice more explicitly (Fainstein, 2014).

In her book *Justice and the Politics of Difference*, Iris Marion Young has presented her vision of “just city” as follows: “As a normative ideal, city life instantiates social relations of difference without exclusion. Different groups dwell in the city alongside one another, of necessity interacting in city spaces. If city politics is to be democratic and not dominated by the point of view of one group, it must be a politics that takes account of and provides voice for the different groups that dwell together in the city without forming a community” (Young, 1990, p. 227). She identifies four main characteristics of this normative ideal of city life: 1) social differentiation without exclusion, 2) variety, 3) eroticism and 4) publicity. Those are presented in the following table (Table 1). In this utopian city, social justice is achieved through the development of a “politics of difference”, namely a politics establishing the institutional and ideological conditions enabling the recognition and affirmation of different social groups. It involves political representations of the different social groups, the celebration of their specific characteristics and cultures, and mutual listening between these groups. Young actually considers that democratising decision-making processes is a prerequisite to undermine domination and oppression (Young, 1990).

Social differentiation without exclusion	Freedom leads to group differentiation, to the formation of affinity groups , but this social and spatial differentiation of groups is without exclusion. The urban ideal expresses difference (...), a side-by-side particularity neither reducible to identity nor completely other. (...) Groups do not stand in relations of inclusion and exclusion, but overlap and intermingle without becoming homogeneous. (...) Borders are open and undecidable. (Young 1990, p. 238 - 239)
Variety	The interfusion of groups in the city occurs partly because of the multiuse differentiation of social space. (...) Both business people and residents tend to have more commitment to and care for such neighborhoods than they do for single-use neighborhoods. Multi-functional streets, parks, and neighborhoods are also much safer than single-use functionalized spaces because people are out on the streets during most hours, and have commitment to the place. (Young 1990, p. 239)
Eroticism	City life also instantiates difference as the erotic, in the wide sense of an attraction to the other , the pleasure and excitement of being drawn out of one's secure routine to encounter the novel, strange, and surprising. (...) The erotic attraction here is precisely the obverse of community. In the ideal of community people feel affirmed because those with whom they share experiences, perceptions, and goals recognize and are recognized by them; one sees oneself reflected in the others. (...) The city's eroticism also derives from the aesthetics of its material being: the bright and colored lights, the grandeur of its buildings, the juxtaposition of architecture of different times, styles, and purposes. (...) The erotic meaning of the city arises from its social and spatial inexhaustibility. (Young 1990, p. 239 - 240)
Publicity	Cities provide important public spaces —streets, parks, and plazas—where people stand and sit together, interact and mingle, or simply witness one another, without becoming unified in a community of "shared final ends." (...) Politics, the critical activity of raising issues and deciding how institutional and social relations should be organized, crucially depends on the existence of spaces and forums to which everyone has access. (...) city life provides public places and forums where anyone can speak and anyone can listen. (Young 1990, p. 240)

Table 1. Characteristics of the vision of the “just city” envisioned by Young (1990)

In the continuity of the work of Iris Marion Young (Pinder, 2002), the urban planner Leonie Sandercock (1997) has envisioned *Cosmopolis*, an utopian city in which difference can flourish. She presents *Cosmopolis* as “an always unfinished and contested construction site” (Sandercock 1997, p. 199), “a Utopian which has more to do with process and becoming, than with achievement and being” (ibid, p. 218). Just like Young (1990), Sandercock emphasises processes towards a just city, pointing to the need to democratise decision-making and to give a central place to the recognition of difference through the formal group representation. She advocates for the advent of a culturally pluralist democracy practising “a politics of inclusion by providing mechanisms for the effective recognition and representation of the distinct voices and perspectives of oppressed and disadvantaged groups” (Sandercock, 1997). In her book, Sandercock sketches a paradigm shift from *Metropolis*, a planning dedicated to a social project tending to eradicate difference which supported the development of modernist cities, to *Cosmopolis*. This shift from *Metropolis* to *Cosmopolis* involves the development of 1) an expanded language for planning, 2) an epistemology of multiplicity, and 3) a transformative politics of difference. The table herunder presents these three guiding principles.

Expanded language for planning	There is a need for diversity of spaces and places in the city: places loaded with visual stimulation, as well as places of quiet contemplation (...). An essential ingredient of planning beyond the modernist paradigm is a reinstatement of inquiry about and recognition of the importance of memory, desire and the spirit (or the sacred) as vital dimensions of healthy human settlements and a sensitivity to cultural differences in the expression of each. (Sandercock 1997, p. 214)
Epistemology of multiplicity	The new approach insists on context-specific negotiations. To enter into negotiation across the gulf of cultural difference requires all participants to be fluent in a range of ways of knowing and communicating: from storytelling to listening to interpreting complex visual languages as well as tribal languages. (...) A more democratic and culturally inclusive planning must draw on many ways of knowing , and must develop a

	<i>sensibility which is able to discern which ways of knowing are most useful in what circumstances. (Sandercock 1997, p. 217)</i>
Transformative politics of difference	<i>There must be an end to the pretence that planning could be a-political or value-neutral. (...) The most promising experiments in insurgent planning have involved mobilized communities forging coalitions to work for broad objectives of economic, environmental, social and cultural justice, and in the process resisting, engaging with, and participating in 'the state'. (Sandercock 1997, p. 217-218)</i>

Table 2. Three guiding principles towards Cosmopolis defined by Sandercock (1997)

3.3. The Communicative Turn

The 90s also witnessed the development of the school of communicative urban planning practice, sometimes referred to as the “communicative (or argumentative) turn”. Inspired by the Habermas’ principle of “ideal speech” (see Habermas, 1984), this school of thought led by theorists like John Forester (1988) considers equal participation in decision-making processes as a prerequisite for ensuring distributive justice in the city, thus highlighting the need for procedural justice (Fischer, 2009 ; Steil and Connolly, 2009). In his influential book *Planning in the face of Power*, John Forester (1988) presents a set of guiding principles for ensuring a substantive democratic planning process: “Problem will be solved not solely by technical experts, but also by pooling expertise and non-professional contributions; not just by formal procedure, but also by informal consultation and involvement; not predominantly by strict reliance on data bases, but also by careful use of trusted resources, contacts and friends; not mainly through formally rational management procedure, but through internal and external politics and the development of a working consensus; not by solving engineering equations, but by complementing technical performance with political sophistication, support-building, liaison work – all this, organizing – and finally, intuition and luck” (Forester 1988, p. 153). Considering the role of initial inequalities (in terms of, e.g., time, resources, expertise or information) in participatory planning processes in the reproduction of inequalities, Forester argues that planners should anticipate and reconfigure power relations in order to develop a communication free from domination. With that aim in mind, he proposes a list of options for planners to correct the communicative distortions.

3.4. The “Just City” Era

At the beginning of the 21st century, the advent of the “neoliberal” city and the associated growth of social and spatial inequalities have led to call for articulating insights from political economy and political philosophy to define visions of the “just city” (Dlabac et al. 2022 ; Granberg and Glover, 2021; Connolly and Steil 2009 ; Novy and Mayer, 2009). A seminal work in this school of thought is the book *The Just City* published by Susan Fainstein (2010). In this book, Fainstein starts from the justice theory of John Rawls and the capability approach elaborated by Martha Nussbaum to sketch the contours of the so-called “Just city”. She describes the “just city” as “one where public investment and regulation would produce equitable outcomes rather than support those already well off” (Fainstein, 2010, p.3). Fainstein’s conception of justice covers three dimensions: equity, democracy, and diversity. These three dimensions mirror respectively distributive justice, procedural justice and recognition (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019). For each of the three dimensions of justice, Fainstein has defined a set of principles to guide planning and policies. Those are presented in the following table (Table 3).

Equity (≈ Distributive justice)	Democracy (≈ Procedural Justice)	Diversity (≈ Recognition)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>All new housing development should provide units for households with income below the median, either on-site or elsewhere, with the goal of providing a decent home and suitable living</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Groups that are not able to participate directly in decision-making processes should be represented by advocates.</i> • <i>Plans should be developed in consultation with the target</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Households should not be required to move for the purpose of obtaining diversity, but neither should new communities be built that further segregation.</i> • <i>Zoning should not be used for</i>

<p><i>environment for everyone (...)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Housing units developed to be affordable should remain in perpetuity in the affordable housing pool or be subject to one-for-one replacement. ● Households or business should not be involuntarily relocated for the purpose of obtaining economic development or community balance except in exceptional circumstances. (...) ● Economic development programs should give priority to the interest of employees and, where feasible, small businesses, which generally are more locally rooted than large corporations. All new commercial development should provide space for public use and when possible should facilitate the livelihood of independent and cooperatively owned businesses. ● Megaprojects should be subject to heightened scrutiny, be required to provide direct benefits to low-income people in the form of employment provisions, public amenities, and a living wage, and, if public subsidy is involved, should include public participation in the profits. (...) ● Fares for intracity transit (but not commuter rail) should be kept very low. (...) Low-income people with no choice but to commute by car should receive rebates. ● Planners should take an active role in deliberative setting in pressing for egalitarian solutions and blocking ones that disproportionately benefit the already well-off. (Fainstein 2010, p.172-173) 	<p><i>population if the area is already developed. The existing population, however, should not be the sole arbiter of the future of an area. Citywide considerations must also apply.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>In planning for as yet uninhabited or sparsely occupied areas, there should be broad consultation that includes representatives of groups currently living outside the affected area. (Fainstein, 2010 p.175)</i> 	<p><i>discriminatory ends but rather should foster inclusion</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Boundaries between districts should be porous</i> ● <i>Ample public space should be widely accessible and varied; where public spaces are provided by private entities, political speech should not be prohibited within the property. At the same time, groups with clashing lifestyles should not have to occupy the same location.</i> ● <i>To the extent practical and desired by affected populations, land uses should be mixed.</i> ● <i>Public authorities should assist groups who have historically suffered from discrimination in achieving access to opportunity in housing, education and employment. (Fainstein, 2010 p.174)</i>
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Table 3. Principles to guide planning and policies in the vision of “Just City” elaborated by Fainstein (2010)

Fainstein adopts a critical posture in relation to the priority given to recognition and procedural justice by the authors of the 90s mentioned above. She considers, on the one hand, that the diversity principle advocated by multicultural theorists is seldom questioned by the latter, while obtaining diversity may conflict with other values, and on the other hand, that procedural justice promoted by communicative theorists is hardly achievable in reality due to pre-existing inequalities, but also that just democratic processes can lead to unjust outcomes (Fainstein, 2014 ; Connolly and Steil, 2009). Fainstein's “Just City” vision has, in turn, been criticised by David Harvey. The latter, who adopts a radical posture by advocating an overthrow of the capitalist order, criticises the work of Fainstein for not questioning the maintenance of the economic and social regime in place. Fainstein indeed asserts, in the first pages of her book, that her “analysis is limited to what appears feasible within the present context of capitalist urbanisation in wealthy, formally democratic, Western countries” (Fainstein, 2010, p.5). For Harvey, “this is precisely the point at which Fainstein’s conception of the Just City falters. From the start, it delimits its scope to acting within the existing capitalist regime of rights and freedoms and is thus

constrained to mitigating the worst outcomes at the margins of an unjust system” (Harvey and Potter 2009, p.46). Faced with this criticism, Fainstein (2010) responds that the establishment of a justice-centred urban governance on a national and international scale could put pressure on the current system and contribute to transforming capitalism into a more humane system. This major disagreement between Harvey and Fainstein reveals an important dividing line between the different visions of the just city, the one opposing “transformative” and “affirmative” conceptions of the “just city”. While the transformative conceptions aim to change the social, economic and/or political system that produces and reproduces urban injustice, affirmative conceptions aim to deal with the injustices generated by the social, economic and/or political system, without changing this system (Granberg and Glover, 2021).

Fainstein's work is part of a long line of literature aimed at understanding the interactions between urban and justice issues to sketch visions of the “just city” (Connolly and Steil, 2009). Among these, we find notably the work of John Friedmann (2000). In the paper *The Good City: In Defense of Utopian Thinking*, John Friedmann imagines the *Good City* as a city that “has its foundations in human flourishing and multipli/city” and in which “four pillars provide for its material foundations: housing, affordable health care, adequately remunerated work and adequate social provision” (Friedmann 2000, p. 471). The four pillars of the *Good City* are described in more detail in the table hereunder (Table 4). Considering procedural justice as equally important as distributive justice, Friedman has also envisioned a *Good City* governance system involving “an autonomous, self-organizing civil society, active in making claims, resisting and struggling on behalf of the good city within a framework of democratic institutions” (Friedmann 2000, p. 471).

Adequate housing	<i>First in importance is socially adequate housing together with complementary public services and community facilities. As innumerable struggles in cities throughout the world have shown, housing needs, along with water and affordable urban transit, are viewed as a first priority of individual households. By common consent, the greatest social disaster (in peacetime) is to be homeless. (Friedmann 2000, p. 468)</i>
Affordable healthcare	<i>Affordable healthcare comes second, particularly for women, infants, the physically and mentally challenged, the chronically ill and the elderly, as a prime condition for human flourishing. (Friedmann 2000, p. 468)</i>
Adequately remunerated work	<i>Adequately remunerated work for all who seek it is the third pillar. In urban market societies, a well-paying job is a nearly universal aspiration not only for the income it brings but for the social regard that attaches to regular work in capitalist society. (Friedmann 2000, p. 468)</i>
Adequate social provision	<i>Finally, adequate social provision in housing, medical care, human services and income must be made for the weakest citizens, if their own efforts are insufficient to provide for what is regarded as the social minimum. (Friedmann 2000, p. 468)</i>

Table 4. Four pillars of the “Good city” envisioned by Young (1990)

Another influential contribution is that of the urban geographer Edward Soja, who has defined the concept of “spatial justice” as “the fair and equitable distribution in space of socially valued resources and the opportunities to use them” (Soja, 2009, p. 2). This concept, which also includes a procedural justice dimension, aims at complementing other forms of justice by providing “an intentional and focused emphasis on the spatial or geographical aspects of justice and injustice” (Soja, 2009, p. 2).

4. Review of the “Sustainable City” Visions

In parallel to visions of the just city, “sustainable” cities vision, such as the Sustainable City, the Green City, the Eco-City, the Low Carbon and Carbon Neutral City, the Smart City, the Circular City, and the Resilient City have been extensively discussed in the academic literature. These visions emerged as responses to different environmental problems and have proposed various solutions. They emphasise to different degrees the role of technological development (e.g., low-carbon technologies, smart technologies...) and the role of urban form (e.g., compactness, greening, connectivity...) in responding to modern environmental and social challenges. The “sustainable” cities visions have mostly taken root in the late 20th century and have been growing in popularity ever since (see their occurrence in the academic literature in Figure 1). Together, they represent the evolving understanding of what it means to be a “sustainable city”. This section explores the key visions of sustainable cities that have emerged over the past few decades, outlining their emergence and key characteristics.

Figure 1: Frequency of keywords in Scopus articles over time (de Jong et al., 2015)

4.1. The Sustainable City

The Sustainable City concept is the most widely used of the concepts detailed in this section and tends to be broader in scope than similar concepts (De Jong et al., 2015). It derived from the “sustainable development” concept and was popularised in the 1990s (De Jong et al., 2015). The UN report, *Our Common Future* (1987) proposed the concept of sustainable development, defined as the ability of humanity “to ensure that it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (p. 16). The development of sustainable cities was first discussed at the UN Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm, which brought to an international stage the need for the development of sustainable patterns of urbanisation (Whitehead, 2003).

Sustainable cities are often understood as cities that work toward sustainable development goals. Many visions refer to the “triple bottom line”, which considers environmental conservation, social justice, or economic efficiency (Blanco and Mazmanian, 2014). The primary guiding principle of the sustainable city is ecological and social sustainability, creating balance between the city and nature (Yanarella and Levine, 1992). Many of the environmental, social, and economic benefits of the

Sustainable City come as a result of its high-density, compact, and mixed-use urban form (Jenks and Jones, 2010). The compact city form will make for shorter travel journeys, safer, easier access to amenities, and reduced car dependency (Jenks and Jones, 2010). The Sustainable City centres social and commercial hubs around public transit nodes (Rogers, 1997). Compactness can lead to improved quality of life by allowing for more social interaction, which can boost community spirit and promote innovation and creativity (Jenks and Jones, 2010). Toward environmental objectives, the vision promotes the use of renewable energy and energy efficiency (Yanarella and Levine, 1992; Rogers, 1997) and consumption in the Sustainable City is reduced by, inter alia, recycling, and reusing resources (Rogers, 1997). Technologies will be used to improve air quality, while vegetation will be implemented to cool the city and provide other environmental benefits (Rogers, 1997). The vision foresees a decentralisation of power toward the hands of the many and involvement of citizens in the evolution of their city, as people should feel a sense of communal ownership and responsibility toward public space (Rogers, 1997). In terms of economic production, the vision prioritises a decentralised and localised model to enhance self-sufficiency (Yanarella and Levine, 1992).

4.2. The Green City

The Green City vision first emerged from a study conducted in southern California in 1976; this vision focused on the promotion of public transport over private car use, adequate provision of pedestrian and cycling systems, expansion of the open space system, and renewal of old buildings for new use (Johnson, 1979). Subsequent visions have remained vague, which is reflected in the definition by Kahn (2006), which states that defining a green city is difficult, although we have an “intuitive” sense of what makes a city a “green city”, e.g., clean air and water, pleasant streets, and parks (p. 4). Definitions often depend on the field in which the term is employed (Breuste, 2023).

There seem to exist two visions of the Green City. The first is a more literal use of the word “green”, in which green is synonymous with nature and refers to enhancement of vegetation networks in cities. An example is the vision put forward by Breuste (2020), in which the Green City is “a city where all forms of nature—living organisms, biocoenosis, and their habitats—are highly significant components of green infrastructure. In a Green City, these forms of nature are preserved, maintained, and extended for the benefit of city residents.” (p. 2). A similar vision is presented by Dekay and O’Brein (2001), who state that the Green City is a place where nature should be positively experienced, where people frequently interact with nature and have freedom of movement and opportunities for immersion in nature. The other category of Green City vision employs the term “green” to refer to general sustainability or eco-friendly concepts (Brilhante and Klaas, 2018), but also consider social responsibility and economic sustainability (Lewis, 2015). Such a green city is characterised by its commitment to environmentally sustainable practices, such as the implementation of green infrastructure, energy efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable transportation (Lewis, 2015). One prominent example comes from *The Green City* by Low et al. (2005), in which the authors describe the elements of a Green City and propose several strategies for creating sustainable urban neighbourhoods by using renewable energy sources, promoting energy-efficient and climate-friendly design, incentivizing sustainable transport, prioritising sustainable water use, increasing the number of green spaces, and promoting social equity. Low et al. (2005) also advocate for shorter travel distance to reach essential amenities, both to reduce environmental impact and to allow people to connect with local neighbours. They advocate for affordable housing, inclusiveness, and special consideration for the housing needs of “the disabled, older people, immigrants, and people of different cultures.”

4.3. The Eco-City

The Eco-City concept began with Richard Register’s creation of the Urban Ecology group in the mid-1970s and the publication of his formative book *Ecocity Berkeley: Building Cities for a Healthy Future* (1987). Register defined an eco-city as an “ecologically healthy city”, existing within the means of the ecological carrying capacity of the city’s bioregion. Newer definitions integrate wider economic and

social issues, which has led to a shift in focus away from the Eco-City's prioritisation of environmental and ecological goals (De Jong et al., 2015).

Today, the Eco-City is broadly understood to be a city that aims to achieve sustainable development goals by integrating environmental, social, and economic dimensions of urban planning and management, again guided by the "triple bottom line". Eco-cities create "compact, diverse, green, safe, pleasant and vital mixed-use communities" close to nodes of transport and transit facilities (Roseland, 1997). They prioritise pedestrian and bike travel over cars, thereby promoting "access by proximity" (Engwicht, 1992; Roseland, 1997; Kenworthy, 2004). Engwicht (1992) stresses that these slow-mobilities can encourage interaction between people, which he says is critical given that modern car-based urban design hinders interaction. Natural environments permeate the Eco-City, and food is produced locally (Roseland, 1997; Kenworthy, 2004). Sustainable practices like recycling and resource conservation discourage excessive material consumption (Roseland, 1997). The Eco-City vision promoted by the Eco-City Builders (continuing from Reger's initial conceptualization) also abides by sustainability objectives by not consuming more resources than it produces and without polluting or damaging itself or nearby ecosystems and also calls attention the need for cities to exist within the means of the Earth's carrying capacity and "ecological integrity" (Ecocity Builders Community, 2010). Other environmental components of Eco-Cities include renewable energy production, maximisation of water and energy efficiency, zero-waste systems (Ecocity Builders Community, 2010), and the use of technology for environmental management (Kenworthy, 2004). The Eco-City offers affordable, high-quality, safe, and diverse mixed housing (Roseland, 1997). The city has a high-quality public sphere to encourage the expression of culture and community (Kenworthy, 2004). Economic performance and job creation are spurred through innovation, creativity, sensitive to the "uniqueness of the local environment, culture and history" (Kenworthy, 2004, p. 68), yet high environmental and social quality are retained through, e.g., environmentally friendly economic activities (Roseland, 1997; Kenworthy, 2004).

4.4. The Low Carbon and Carbon Neutral City

The concept of the low carbon city has gained traction across the world in response to climate change, focusing on reducing carbon emissions and minimising non-renewable energy use (de Jong et al., 2015). This vision draws on the concept of the low carbon economy, introduced in a UK Government's Energy White Paper in 2003 (Department of Trade and Industry, 2003), and is often used when defining a low carbon city (de Jong et al., 2015). According to this white paper, a low carbon economy seeks to reduce environmental harms through energy efficiency, low carbon energy generation, low carbon transport, productivity, competitiveness and innovation.

In the same vein, despite the lack of a clear vision (Tozer and Klenk, 2018), the low carbon city usually considers improved living standards and economic output through technological innovation while reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Cheng et al., 2019). A low carbon city ideally embodies a model of urban construction and social development that prioritizes reduced carbon emissions and encourages citizens to lower their own carbon footprints, without sacrificing their overall quality of life. Specifically, the emphasis is placed on high energy efficiency, low carbon energy sources (including low carbon transport) (Tan et al., 2017) - largely influenced by engineering and economic thinking (de Jong et al., 2015). However, some scholars also envision changes in resident lifestyles, towards less energy intensive consumption habits (e.g., Wu et al., 2022; Zhang and Zheng, 2023). Variants of the low carbon city, like zero carbon (Kansara and Ridley, 2012) and carbon neutral cities emphasise carbon offsetting in achieving climate targets (Tozer and Klenk, 2018). Carbon neutrality offers flexibility by allowing emission offsets purchased from third parties (Damsø et al., 2017; Gössling, 2009; Kennedy and Sgouridis, 2011). The concept gained traction after the Special IPCC Report on 1.5°C in 2018, which called for net-zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 (Huovila et al., 2022).

4.5. The Smart City

The roots of the concept of smart city can be traced back as early as 1974, when the city of Los Angeles attempted to create the world's first urban big data project (Sharifi et al., 2021). However, it was not until 1994 that a major milestone in the pursuit of smart cities occurred in Amsterdam, when a virtual “digital city” was created with the purpose of promoting internet usage among local populations (Alberts et al., 2017). The more modern concept of “smart city” first appeared in the literature in 1998 (Van Bastelaer, 1998). The smart city concept has since then gained increasing importance in the agendas of policy makers and the private sector.

Despite its fuzzy meaning (Anthopoulos and Fitsilis, 2013), the smart city vision is generally understood as a combination of green city ideals and technological futurism (Vanolo, 2014). Neirotti et al. (2014) describe it as a paradigm of intelligent urban development, focusing on sustainable economic growth. Sharifi et al. (2021) identify Caragliu et al. (2011) as the most influential article in the exponentially growing literature on smart cities. Caragliu et al. propose six characteristics of a smart city, including interconnected infrastructure, business-driven urban development, social inclusion, ICT and high-tech infrastructures, human capital, and social and environmental sustainability.

At least three distinct focuses of smart cities can be identified: an economy-centric vision, seeking competitiveness and productivity (e.g., IBM, 2019); a sustainability-centric vision focused on environmental footprint reduction, or aligned with the concept of “sustainable development” (e.g., Bibri and Krogstie, 2017; Höjer and Wangel, 2015; Kramers et al., 2014); and a human-centric vision centred on inclusiveness, privacy and well-being (e.g., Hollands, 2008; Eckhoff and Wagner, 2018). Smart cities have gained importance in policy makers' agendas since the late 2000s, offering innovation and investment opportunities in urban development (Caragliu et al., 2011; Anthopoulos et al., 2016). Major ICT corporations such as Cisco and IBM have led the development of digital infrastructures, advocating for a utopian smart city narrative (Söderström et al., 2014; Sharifi et al., 2021). In this way, the smart city promotes engineering system solutions to urban problems and has somewhat shifted attention away from key environmental issues of the city to ones oriented towards infrastructure and information use (de Jong et al., 2015). This technology-oriented approach poses potential risks, such as perpetuating power imbalances and limiting alternative urban solutions (Vanolo, 2014). Recognizing these concerns, there has been a recent shift towards more holistic approaches, incorporating social, economic, and institutional forces (Sharifi et al., 2021).

4.6. The Circular City

Urbanisation has increased resource consumption and waste generation, leading to global ecological impact and urban ecosystem degradation (Williams, 2021). Recently, there has been a growing interest in transitioning towards circular economies in cities (Ashton et al., 2022). The circular city concept has evolved from industrial ecology (1960s) and its focus on industrial symbiosis (Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989), cradle-to-cradle design (1990s) advocating closed-loop systems (McDonough and Braungart, 2002), and the circular economy (late 1990s-2000s) emphasising resource management and regeneration (Stahel, 2016). The Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2010) has been instrumental in popularising the circular economy concept to urban environments, aiming to create sustainable, resilient, and liveable urban areas by minimising waste, optimising resource use, and promoting local and regenerative resource loops.

A synthesis definition of a circular city suggests it “is based on closing, slowing and narrowing the resource loops as far as possible after the potential for conservation, efficiency improvements, resource sharing, servitization and virtualization has been exhausted, with remaining needs for fresh material and energy being covered as far as possible based on local production using renewable natural resources” (Paiho et al., 2020, pp. 6-7). Some circular city visions focus on reuse and closing loops of material resources (Prendeville et al., 2018), while others apply the concept of circular economy more broadly, additionally considering resource efficiency, renewable energy, local production, and/or

servitization (Bocken et al., 2016; Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015; Circular Cities Hub, 2017). Williams (2021) underscores also the role of adaptation and ecological regeneration in circular cities. This involves flexible infrastructure, collaborative processes promoting community learning and self-organisation, urban ecosystems management, and bioremediation processes. The Circular Cities Declaration (2020) emphasises the importance of promoting a circular economy in cities to decouple economic growth from resource use and environmental harm while improving human well-being, reducing emissions, protecting biodiversity, and promoting social justice, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals.

4.7. The Resilient City

The resilience concept emerged in the late 20th century in response to concerns about the impacts of urbanisation, climate change, and socio-economic disparities on urban stability and sustainability. Initially popularised in ecology, resilience theory focused on ecosystems' capacity to absorb shocks, maintain structure, and undergo adaptive transformations (Holling, 1973). In the 1990s, resilience theory expanded to include social-ecological systems, acknowledging the interdependence between human societies and their environment (Berkes and Folke, 1998). This shift recognized the need to address biophysical aspects of urban resilience, as well as socio-economic dimensions such as social equity, economic vitality, and governance structures (Pickett, Cadenasso, and Grove, 2004).

Initially, the approach to resilience focused on the capacity of cities to protect their inhabitants from extreme shocks (Meerow et al., 2016; Nunes, Pinheiro, and Tome, 2019), especially on the ability for a swift recovery and efficiency to regain stability after destabilising events (Lamond and Proverbs, 2009). However, the resilient city soon developed into a vision for the governance of intertwined urban social and natural systems (Oliver et al., 2015; Kotilainen, Eisto, and Vatanen, 2015). This approach has tended to shift from a descriptive (resilience as a property) to a normative approach (resilience as an objective) for urban sustainability management that encapsulates all facets of urban life (Chelleri, 2012; Hassler and Kohler, 2014; Bruzzone et al., 2021).

Resilient cities are envisioned as urban areas with the ability to adapt and recover from various challenges while maintaining core functions and vitality, addressing ecological, infrastructural, social, and institutional aspects (Meerow et al., 2016). These cities aim to minimise vulnerabilities, enhance adaptive capacities, and promote long-term sustainability, ensuring the well-being of inhabitants and preserving essential urban services and resources (Gunderson and Holling, 2002; Godschalk, 2003). According to Prasad et al. (2009), “[r]esilient cities in the light of climate change should be able to develop plans for future development and growth, bearing in mind the climate impacts that the urban systems are likely to face.” These cities incorporate innovative planning and design strategies to accommodate changes in urban form, infrastructure, and environmental conditions. Such strategies include green infrastructure, flexible zoning regulations, and mixed land use, which help reduce urban heat islands, manage stormwater, and promote biodiversity (Ahern, 2011). Resilient cities also emphasise social capital and community engagement, which are crucial for building adaptive capacities and reducing vulnerability (Lebel et al., 2006; Romero-Lankao and Dodman, 2012). The Rockefeller Foundation's 100 Resilient Cities initiative (2013-2019) significantly advanced the concept of resilient city by providing resources, strategies, and network support to 100 selected cities (The Rockefeller Foundation, s. d.).

5. Sustainability and Justice Objectives in the Reviewed Visions

5.1. Sustainability Objectives in the “Just City” Visions

The visions of the “just city” consider only in a limited way contemporary environmental problems, the sustainability transitions they call for and the justice issues associated with these transitions. This observation is shared by Granberg and Glover who affirm that “Fainstein’s just city concept fails to take socio-environmental dynamics into account” (Granberg and Glover 2021, p. 6). In the same line, Hughes and Hoffmann state that “there are typically few explicit links to environmental or climate change concerns in scholarship on the just city” (Hughes and Hoffmann 2019, p.6).

Several authors mentioned above, including Leonie Sandercock (1997), Suzan Fainstein (2010) and Johan Friedmann (2000), identify sustainability as a key component of a normative ideal of the city, but they do not define explicitly what a sustainable city should look like. This limitation is acknowledged by the authors themselves, starting with Fainstein, who states that “The discussion does not go so far as to investigate the broader concept of the good city. Justice is only one component of the good city. (...) The analysis is limited to the relations between equity, diversity and democracy, which I indicated earlier to be the principal components of urban justice. (...) I do not focus on some considerations - for example, good city form or environmental sustainability - that would be encompassed in more expansive investigation” (Fainstein 2010, p. 58). In the same way, Friedmann leaves this search for “sustainable city” to specialists in urban environmental issues: “Also missing from my account is any reference to the ‘sustainable’ city, which I am prepared to leave to the experts who will want to talk, more knowledgeably than I, about resource-conserving cities, blue skies and clear water” (Friedmann 2000, p. 471). Finally, Sandercock (1997) calls for the development of interdisciplinary approaches to urban habitat issues. Considering that the damage made by the modernist planning paradigm to the environment is one of the most basic and important processes shaping the urban habitat, she indeed advocates for articulating the literature on human-environmental relations and that on urban planning.

Regarding the justice issues associated with environmental questions, we find in several visions of “just city”, like that of Fainstein (2010) and Johan Friedmann (2000), some dimensions of environmental justice such as the access to a quality living environment, decent housing, water and public transport for all. In her work, Susan Fainstein further highlights the distributive issues linked to environmental policies: “In environmental policy, as in so many areas, often the most efficient way to achieve objectives is to invest in programs that primarily benefit the well-off - that is, programs to remove land from potential development, thereby raising the price of available housing sites, or subsidising new, higher-density construction in inner cities that promotes gentrification” (Fainstein 2010, p. 54). Based on this observation, she integrates into her vision of the “just city” principles of urban governance aimed at preventing rising house prices and involuntary relocations as part of urban transformation strategies, including environmental policies. For her part, Sandercock (1997) considers the shift from *Metropolis* to *Cosmopolis*, and more particularly the advent of a culturally pluralist democracy, as a way to address social, cultural, but also environmental justice issues. She states that “we must develop group-conscious social and urban and environmental policies, and that it is not likely to happen unless oppressed social groups are represented in decision-making forums” (Sandercock 1997, p. 186).

Climate and energy justice are, however, systematically absent from the “just city” visions reviewed. These visions do, indeed, include neither justice issues related to the impacts of climate change, nor those associated with energy production and consumption systems. The absence of climate and energy justice in the visions of the “just city” reviewed is notably related to the time in which these visions were developed, namely between 1990 and 2010. As shown by Reece (2018), equity planning and theory has evolved over time in responses to broad societal and economic factors. He shows that the concept of “just city” emerged in the early 2000s to address issues such as immigration and globalisation, growing inequality, gentrification, as well as social and racial conflicts. This could

contribute to explain the fact that in the “just city” visions, environmental problems are mainly addressed through the environmental justice issues raised by gentrification processes related to environmental policies, while climate and energy justice are systematically absent. These last issues are much more recent. As mentioned previously (see Section 1), the emergence of the literature on energy justice and the consideration of climate justice issues at the urban level are located after 2010 (Heffron and McCauley, 2017 ; Bulkeley et al., 2014).

Finally, the “just city” visions tend to focus on justice for the human being here and now. As a result, they do not consider justice for the inhabitants of southern countries, future generations and non-humans which are important issues in the context of contemporary environmental problems. Quoting the work of Scott Campbell (2003), Fainstein (2010) evokes the complexity of considering distributive justice to future generations and to other species by pointing out the possible contradictions with justice for present generations.

Against that background, we argue that urban justice theorists and planners would benefit from entering fully into a new area, that of the just transition in order to respond to contemporary socio-environmental challenges. The articulation between “just city” and “sustainable city” visions will be discussed in more detail in the last section of the paper (see Section 6 “Towards “Just Urban Transition” Visions Reconciling Justice and Sustainability objectives”).

5.2. Justice Objectives in the “Sustainable City” Visions

Social justice considerations are central to the Sustainable City, Eco-City, and Green City visions. As stated in his book, *Cities for a Small Planet* (1999), which discusses the creation of the Sustainable City, Rogers states that “Poverty, unemployment, ill-health, poor education, conflict – in short, social injustice in all its forms – undermine a city's capacity to be environmentally sustainable. [...] There can be no urban harmony or real environmental improvements without basic human rights and peace.” In other words, social justice is not one element of the Sustainable City but is central for the environmental, social, and economic sustainability of the city. It is of note that the Green City vision is perhaps less transformative than the Sustainable and Eco-City visions. For example, in the vision of Low et al. (2005), the authors stress that we must work within our means and within imperfect systems to simultaneously deliver ecological sustainability, social justice, and economic success while also advocating for individuals and their rights. Further, certain justice elements are discussed in some visions but not others; this will be detailed in the following paragraphs.

These Sustainable City (i.e., the Sustainable City, Eco-City, and Green City) visions predominantly address challenges of distributive injustice through the compact city form. In their discussion of the Sustainable City, Jenks and Jones (2010) cite the 1999 Urban Task Force report *Towards an Urban Renaissance*, which states that having a variety of uses and the means to access them nearby is key to achieving social equity, particularly for the most disadvantaged in society who may otherwise lack access to resources. Compactness, mixed use, and equally distributed green will result in better access to goods and benefits by all, i.e., access by proximity (Register, 1987; Jenks and Jones, 2010). Similarly, the Eco-City model necessitates the provision of affordable, safe housing with “operational facilities and services” to all (Eco-City Builders. 2011). Green City visions, which take a narrow view of “green” to mean “vegetated”, focus only on equality in the distribution of urban green and access to urban green and its related social and environmental benefits.

Procedural justice is mainly assured through true democratic participation in planning and decision-making. The different visions consider various elements of ensuring democracy. For instance, Yanarella and Levine (1992) call for a decentralisation of power and economy, such that decision-making returns to the hands of citizens. The authors state that through experimentation and changes to the existing urban fabric, “dissatisfied city dwellers and other change agents” should be able to “translate their homes into social processes” (p. 306). They envision the creation of common meeting grounds and shared spaces that cross between and intersect different urban spheres (e.g., government,

coeducation, religion). Roseland (1997) says the sustainable city will equip citizens with tools to effectively participate in society. Central to this is the introduction of educational projects to increase public awareness of ecological and sustainability challenges (Roseland, 1997). Similarly, Rogers (1997) states that “teaching children about their everyday urban environment equips them to participate in the process of respecting and improving the city. We must teach good citizenship to young and old, and listen to citizens” (p. 17). The Eco-City Builders (2011) add to this the promotion of feminist ethics of care as “societies that care for each other achieve fuller participation in decision-making processes”.

These visions also make several considerations regarding justice by recognition. For instance, Roseland (1997) says that Eco-Cities create opportunities for minority and vulnerable groups, such as women, people of colour, and the disabled. Similarly, the Sustainable City will confront race, class, gender divisions in part through the creation of common meeting grounds and interconnecting and overlapping spheres and institutions of urban life and by shifting power imbalance (Yanarella and Levine, 1992; Rogers, 1999). According to Roseland (1997), given the diversity of needs and contexts, sustainability should be defined from a local perspective, and the movement will likely take different forms in different countries and contexts. Questions of rights to land ownership and integration of native worldviews are also mentioned in Roseland’s eco-city vision (1997). As early as 1997, Roseland’s Eco-City vision called for integration of the native world view and eco-feminist paradigms in the Eco-City vision. While these visions do address the need for ecosystem health and biodiversity, this tends to be framed to the benefit of human health. Therefore, considerations of the rights of non-human species and their entitlements are not central.

Contrary to Sustainable City, Eco-City, and Green City visions, the lack of consideration for justice issues is a common theme across low carbon and carbon neutral cities, circular cities, smart cities, and, to some extent, resilient cities. In the vision of low carbon or carbon neutral cities, the focus is predominantly on technical solutions to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions, which Kenis and Lievens (2017) argue might be inherently post-political, sidelining social, political, and economic dimensions of the transition. Critics of the smart city concept concur, suggesting that an overemphasis on technology may lead to exclusion or marginalisation of certain urban residents and reduce urban visioning to a single technology-centric future (Hollands, 2008, 2015; Kitchin, 2016). Consequently, justice in smart city debates is often elusive and underdeveloped (Rosol and Blue, 2022). Similarly, most discussions on circular cities have largely ignored explicit discussions of justice (Berry et al., 2022). However, recent literature recognizes the importance of incorporating justice-related issues in circular city planning and implementation (Ashton et al., 2022; Lesniewska and Steenmans, 2023). In the context of resilient cities, although social cohesion is recognised to play a significant role in fostering community resilience (Aldrich and Meyer, 2015), numerous authors contend that the resilience agenda inherently leans towards conservatism and often perpetuates an existing unjust status quo (Cretney, 2014; MacKinnon and Derickson, 2012; Doorn, 2017; Walker and Cooper, 2011; Welsh, 2014). While some resilience scholars underscore the need for equity (e.g., Jabareen, 2013), for Fainstein (2015, 2018), it is not often envisioned in a politically feasible way.

Distributive justice concerns in low carbon and carbon neutral cities, smart cities, circular economies, and urban resilience initiatives often reveal that marginalized and vulnerable populations face disproportionately negative impacts, highlighting the need for a more inclusive and equitable approach to address these inequalities. Social issues are indeed often considered as byproducts of low carbon and carbon neutral cities that need to be addressed with separate measures. For example, the UK Government's Energy White Paper, a foundational document for low-carbon cities (see Section 4.4), primarily addresses energy poverty by envisioning enhanced energy efficiency to make heating more affordable for all, which avoids the question of distribution. Additionally, it suggests the use of vaguely defined “grant schemes” (Department of Trade and Industry, 2003, p. 15). These proposals seem to be considered minor social compensations rather than a central focus on distributive justice. Some form of distributive justice can be found, though, in low carbon city’s emphasis on satisfying the needs of future generations, inherited from the concept of sustainable development. Similarly, while some

scholars advocate for a more human-centric vision of the smart city (e.g. Hollands, 2008; Eckhoff and Wagner, 2018), digital technologies in smart cities may also exacerbate distributional injustices (Söderström et al., 2014; Hollands 2008, 2015). Smart cities may rely on racialized and gendered individuals who engage in unpaid domestic work, low-paid caring and reproductive labour, and volunteer work (Burns and Andrucki, 2021). Put in practice, this vision would lead to urban spaces primarily benefiting technical elites, who are predominantly white, male, and cis-normative (Wiig and Wyly 2016; Rosol and Blue, 2022). Despite the potential for job creation and enhanced living standards, the unequal distribution of costs and benefits among different social groups is often overlooked in circular economy visions, including circular cities (Fratini et al., 2019; Krueger et al., 2018). Regarding resilient cities, critical scholars emphasise that these cities risk “bouncing back” to a previously unjust state, disproportionately benefitting wealthier populations (Fainstein, 2015; Nagenborn, 2019; Vale, 2014). In this regard, Nagenborn (2019) proposes the idea of “bouncing forward”, which envisions the use of adverse events to transform the city towards more (distributive) justice.

Procedural justice is often overlooked in low carbon and carbon neutral cities, smart cities, and circular cities, resulting in limited participatory governance and decision-making that may perpetuate existing power structures and exclude diverse stakeholders from actively shaping their urban environments. These narratives can inhibit equal participation by treating citizens as mere consumers and sensors, instead of active shapers or owners of digital technologies (Cardullo and Kitchin, 2017; Viitanen and Kingston, 2014; Ribera-Fumaz, 2019). Circular economy and circular cities, due to their technical focus, do not explicitly address justice in decision-making. Moreover, Geissdoerfer et al. (2017) show that in general the Circular Economy vision mainly emphasises collaboration between governments and businesses, rather than engaging a broader range of stakeholders. According to Jabareen (2013), a city with greater resilience is characterised by inclusive decision-making processes, open dialogue, accountability, and collaboration in urban planning. However, Fainstein (2015) points out that the resilience concept can often mask politics and power dynamics and assumes an absence of structural conflicts in metropolitan areas.

In the same way, recognition justice tends to be under-addressed in the visions of low carbon and carbon neutral cities, smart cities, and circular cities, potentially leading to the exclusion of marginalised groups and exacerbation of existing vulnerabilities while neglecting the importance of inclusive policies and decision-making processes. While low carbon transitions have the potential to create new or exacerbate existing vulnerabilities, particularly for disadvantaged groups, low carbon and carbon neutral city approaches often do not explicitly recognize the issues related to vulnerable populations. Similarly, dominant smart city visions tend to overlook social vulnerabilities and identities (Rose, 2020). To counter this, Rosol and Blue (2022) emphasise the need to address intersectional, diverse, and inclusive digital geographies, urging for an expansion of focus beyond Western normative conceptions of justice. Recognition justice is also often neglected in the literature on the circular economy and city. Some authors highlight the exclusion of marginalised groups in circular economy policy and planning, pointing out overlooked power dynamics and the limited representation of informal waste workers (Ashton et al., 2022). Marginalised communities, which often engage in circular practices, may be overlooked by formal circular economy policies (Gyori, 2022; Jalas and Numminen, 2022; Nogueira and Wallig, 2022). Ensuring the inclusion of these communities in policy design and implementation can not only promote recognition justice but also support distributive and procedural justice efforts. To promote justice while enhancing resilience, various authors stress the importance of recognizing the rights of all inhabitants (Sapountzaki, 2014; Ziervogel et al., 2017), including vulnerable and marginalised groups in planning and evaluation processes (Doorn, 2017), and prioritising the needs of the most vulnerable populations (Doorn, 2017; Fainstein, 2015). This approach goes beyond merely avoiding injustice during city rebuilding, aiming to actively promote justice throughout the process (Nagenborn, 2019).

6. Towards “Just Urban Transition” Visions Reconciling Justice and Sustainability objectives

6.1. Synergies between Just and Sustainable City Visions

The review of just and sustainable cities visions enables us to identify elements that could make up “just urban transition” visions reconciling justice and sustainability objectives. There are indeed some overlaps between the just and sustainable city visions reviewed which could serve as a basis for building a vision of a just and sustainable city. This is more particularly the case of Sustainable city, Eco-city and Green city visions which, as shown in the previous section (see Section 5.2. Justice Objectives in the “Sustainable City” Visions), give a central place to social justice considerations.

These sustainable city visions thus share several characteristics with the different “just city” visions, starting with those centring distributive justice developed under the “Just City” Era. This is notably the case of the provision of affordable and decent housing for all, which is found both in the “just city” visions elaborated by Susan Fainstein (2010) and John Friedman (2000) and in the Green and Eco city visions. In the same way, the provision of a suitable living environment for everyone advocated by Fainstein echoes the fair distribution of urban green and access to urban green included in the Sustainable and Green city visions. The very low fares for intracity transit also present in Fainstein's “just city” vision can be related to the promotion of public transports over private car use which constitutes one of the key characteristics of the Sustainable city, Eco-city and Green city visions.

These visions of sustainable cities also have similarities characteristics with the “just city” visions centring recognition developed as part of the cultural turn. The “just city” visions developed by Iris Marion Young (1990) and Leonie Sandercock (1997) give an important place to the diversity of space and place in the city, a characteristic also present in the Sustainable and Eco city visions, which involve mixed-use associated with compact urban form. The provision of public spaces where people stand and sit together, interact and mingle advocated by Young is also found in the Sustainable city, Eco and Green city visions. Indeed, in these visions, the compactness, the deployment of slow mobilities and the implementation of parks intend to promote social interactions in the city (Jenk and Jones, 2010 ; Engwicht, 1992).

Finally, procedural justice is found - according to different degrees of priority - in the visions of both “just” and “sustainable” cities. More particularly, both the visions of the “just city” developed as part of the cultural and communicative turn and those of the Sustainable city, Eco-city and Green city call for a deepening of democracy with the participation of citizens in urban planning.

The synergies between just and sustainable city visions go, however, beyond those common characteristics. More fundamentally, the transition to a “sustainable city” is a condition for the transition to a “just city”, and conversely, the transition to a “just city” is a prerequisite for the transition to a “sustainable city”. On the one hand, the environmental problems exacerbate social inequalities, thus hampering the advent of a “just city”. It is indeed clearly established that environmental degradations, including climate change, tend to disproportionately affect the socially and economically marginalised urban dwellers, thus deepening social inequalities (IPCC, 2023). Socio-economically disadvantaged populations tend to be more vulnerable to climate risks because of higher sensitivity, enhanced exposure, and/or reduced capacities to adapt to these risks (de Muynck et al., 2022 ; Kazmierczak et al., 2015). On the other hand, poverty and social inequalities impede sustainability transitions, for two major reasons. First, social, financial or informational barriers prevent less privileged urban dwellers from participating in the sustainability urban transitions, which can compromise the society-wide transformations that are needed for ensuring such transitions. Then, inequalities in participation in decision-making processes can result in unjust environmental policies,

which can lead to social resistance and policy failure, as evidenced by the case of the yellow vests in France (Berry and Laurent, 2019).

6.2. Conflicts between Just and Sustainable City Visions

Reconciling just and sustainable city visions often presents a conundrum due to the complexities of balancing social justice, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. Eloi Laurent (2021) frames these aspects as an “impossible trinity” or a “trilemma,” highlighting the inherent challenge of simultaneously fostering a welfare state, GDP growth, and an ecological transition (see Figure 2).

Under the lens of a just urban transition, Laurent's “welfare state” relates closely to social equity, democracy, and diversity - central tenets of the just city visions. In contrast, GDP growth reflects the focus on economic development, as seen in core ideas of low-carbon, circular, and smart city models. Lastly, the ecological transition corresponds to the shift toward environmentally friendly practices, which characterise sustainable city visions more broadly.

Figure 2. The welfare State - GDP growth - Ecological transition trilemma. Reproduced from Laurent (2021, p. 5)

As Campbell (1996) contends, “[i]n an ideal world, planners would strive to achieve a balance of all three goals. In practice, however, professional and fiscal constraints drastically limit the leeway of most planners” (p. 297). Laurent's trilemma sheds light on inherent tensions among these visions:

1. Welfare versus GDP Growth: Cities that prioritise social equity and welfare, as suggested in the just city vision, could encounter difficulties in achieving sustained economic growth. This conflict manifests, for example, when resources allocated to affordable public housing and social services may divert from stimulating GDP growth through infrastructure projects or business development initiatives.
2. Welfare versus Ecological Transition: Cities focusing on social equity may grapple with balancing affordable housing with the investment in environmental sustainability measures.
3. GDP Growth versus Ecological Transition: Cities that prioritise economic growth might neglect environmental sustainability, due to the huge and unsolved challenge of decoupling economic activity from environmental harms in a sufficient way (Haberl et al., 2020).

In this context, Gilbert's (2014) insights in her article *Social Justice and the 'Green' City* provide a complementary perspective. Drawing on Harvey's *Social Justice and the City*, Gilbert argues that social justice - closely linked to Laurent's idea of the 'welfare state' - has been neglected in sustainability discourses driving the creation of greener cities.

In fact, Gilbert critiques the prevailing notion of sustainability, the triple-bottom-line, which she argues, often serves profit-driven agendas, thereby exacerbating social divides Gilbert argues that sustainability as it is now conceived, as the triple-bottom line, “mobilises the environment at the service of profit-driven agendas, which further exacerbates social divides” (p. 159) - a reflection of the

conflict between welfare state and GDP growth in Laurent's trilemma. The three pillars of sustainability often depict economic, environmental, and social dimensions of sustainability as "equal", while, in actuality, the economic pillar is often prioritised above the social and environmental pillars. This echoes Laurent's argument about the difficulty of achieving a balance among the three aspects of his trilemma. Gilbert claims that urban sustainability objectives have typically been more concerned with "ecological modernization" and "the reproduction of best practices" rather than socio-spatial justice imperatives (p. 160), which aligns with the conflicts Laurent describes.

Gilbert argues that addressing social injustice involves more than redistributing environmental and economic opportunities. Instead, it calls for recognizing that certain "sustainable" practices might intensify existing inequalities. This critique resonates with Laurent's concern about the potential tensions between a welfare state and an ecological transition. She goes on to stress that, when we speak of social injustice, it is not simply a matter of redistributing environmental and economic opportunities, but also of recognizing that certain so-called "sustainable" practices may also obscure or exacerbate existing inequalities. Moreover, current sustainability discourses do not necessarily ensure social justice by building a "new social order based on equality and justice for all in every aspect of social life", but rather often reinforces an unjust status quo. As it stands, most sustainability rhetoric is still situated in "green neoliberalism" and "eco-capitalism". Gilbert states "[a] green or sustainable economy does not automatically fulfil redistributive justice if what is sustained is the same urbanism driven by profits and inequalities - even when presented in a slightly greener shade" (p. 165). In sum, "the tensions between the three pillars of sustainability are not only due to the facts that capitalism is built on social inequalities and environmental injustices but also in the fact that the environmental and social are weighted differently and manipulated more easily in such system" (p. 166).

Overall, bridging different just and sustainable city visions is complex and challenging, as there are inherent tensions and conflicts between the goals of social justice, economic development, and environmental sustainability. The ways of addressing these conflicts are not neutral but associated with broader societal visions, which are inherently political questions.

6.3. Newer Concepts Reconciling Just and Sustainable City Visions

It is important to mention that some literature, particularly more recently, has attempted to bridge the gap between the just and sustainable cities. In this section, we will highlight a few examples of visions that explicitly combine social and sustainability justice objectives and highlight the "gaps" they fill in terms of important justice considerations not captured in the visions above. This is not meant to provide an exhaustive list, but rather to illustrate examples of visions that are already attempting to bridge these gaps.

A notable text is Houghton's *Environmental Justice and the Sustainable City* (1999). The main message of the text is captured in the following quote: "The unjust society is unlikely to be sustainable in environmental or economic terms; the social tensions that are created undermine the recognition of reciprocal rights and obligations, leading to environmental degradation and ultimately to political breakdown" (pg. 2). In other words, Houghton stresses that justice and sustainability objectives cannot be taken alone, but are rather inextricably linked, as a city that is unsustainable is necessarily unjust. In this vision, emphasis is placed on the need to look beyond the simple existence of environmental inequality and toward the systems that generate environmental degradation. Houghton says, "Some have begun to question whether a narrow equity concern with distributional aims may have the unintended perverse effect of overshadowing more broadly constituted justice concerns by addressing underlying structural issues" (p. 1). Beyond this, Houghton calls for attention to the rights of future generations and present-day socially marginalised groups, but also to non-human dimensions and their right to continued existence (i.e., ecological justice).

A recent vision of note, the "just ecofeminist healthy city", comes from Margarita Triguero-Mas et al. (2022) in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors propose the incorporation of "care,

intersectional social inequalities, and environmental justice to the healthy cities approach” (p. 355). The “health city” movement calls for equity, participatory governance, and solidarity, yet the focus on equity in these visions is underdeveloped and does not engage with “deeper” articulations of justice. On the other hand, the “caring city”, which finds its roots in feminist urbanism theory, centres care for the environment and people, while also enabling citizens to care for themselves and others, yet remains largely anthropocentric. The authors state that the COVID-19 pandemic made evident the need to redefine healthy cities and to adopt caring city, environmental justice, and just ecofeminist ethics. The approach reinforces intersectionality, thereby highlighting the different ways people “understand, value, sense, and live the urban environment” (p. 356). Finally, this approach acknowledges the interconnectedness between humans, non-humans, and health.

Another vision for the just and sustainable transformation of cities revolves around the concept of “degrowth”. Degrowth is an umbrella concept that advocates for reducing production and consumption in order to achieve a more sustainable and equitable society (Schmelzer et al., 2022). In urban contexts, the concept has recently gained traction as it helps to align city development with social and environmental well-being, challenging the prevalent growth-and-profit-oriented model (Krähmer, 2021, 2022; Savini, 2021; Xue & Kębłowski, 2022). This transformative approach endorses local economies that value social and environmental targets over profit, through supporting local farming, renewable energy, and other sustainable sectors that serve community and environmental needs, rather than global corporate interests. Further, degrowth fosters equitable and inclusive urban spaces. By advocating affordable housing, public transportation, and other accessible public goods, it envisions a city that caters to all, irrespective of income or social standing (Savini, 2021). Moreover, degrowth champions participatory, democratic decision-making, especially via community-led initiatives that consider people's needs over profit-led interests and other influential forces (Muraca 2012). However, adapting the degrowth concept to cities is an ongoing challenge. For example, noting that degrowth studies have a limited conceptualization of space, Khrämer (2022) asks “how to spatialise degrowth beyond the local scale, not reducing the argument to a dualism between local = good and global = bad?” (p. 316). Nevertheless, the urban degrowth vision may stimulate thinking for reconciling social and environmental objectives, falling in line with the “just transition” paradigm (see Section 6.2).

6.4. Going Forwards

This paper has attempted to confront just city and sustainably city visions in order to understand and explore what a just and sustainable city might look like, but also to identify important justice considerations that have not been captured in either of these visions. Going forward, there are undoubtedly additional dimensions of justice that should be considered (beyond distributive, procedural, and recognition), yet have not been thoroughly captured in both this paper and in existing justice visions. These include, among others, enabling capabilities, restorative justice, and preventative justice (Anguelovski et al., 2020). Restorative and preventative justice are particularly important as reaching a truly sustainable city requires that social justice should address both past and future uneven development processes (Gilbert, 2014).

Reflecting on visions of just and sustainable cities can help to understand toward which future(s) the just transition should orient. That being said, it is important to stress that there is undeniably a disconnect between these visions and their actual implementation, due in part to the tensions outlined above. As it stands, sustainability remains a “branding” in many contexts (Garcia-Lamarca, 2021). For example, in the United Kingdom, “eco-towns” are being constructed as zero carbon developments to support UK carbon reduction targets, yet these are arguably not sustainable, as they are situated on green field sites (Revill and Davies, 2008), and do not meet the other targets of the eco-city vision outlined above. It is therefore important that the implementations of these “visions” are not conflated with the visions themselves.

To address the conflicts arising from the “impossible trinity,” urban planners and policymakers could adopt a holistic and integrated approach that considers the interdependencies between social justice, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. This may involve:

1. Engaging diverse stakeholders, including marginalised communities, in the decision-making process to ensure that their needs and perspectives are taken into account. Recognizing and addressing the power dynamics and inequalities that may exist within urban planning processes is essential for bridging the gap between just city and sustainable city visions.
2. In the context of just urban transitions, exploring strategies that address both social justice and environmental sustainability. It is likely to require moving away from growth as an objective and from capitalist logics more broadly, to navigate the welfare-growth-transition trilemma.
3. Anticipating, monitoring and evaluating the (possible) impacts of just urban transition policies and interventions on different population groups to identify and address any unintended consequences.

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